

Relationship Between Community Structure of Zooplankton and Water Quality in Bojonegara Coastal Area, Banten Bay, Indonesia

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Abstract. Banten Bay is under pressure from industry and sand mining. One area widely used is Bojonegara District. This pressure can trigger changes in water quality. Changes in physical and chemical parameters can affect the life of aquatic biota, one of which is zooplankton. This study aims to analyze the community structure (abundance, diversity, evenness, and dominance) of zooplankton and the relationship between zooplankton and water quality in the waters around Bojonegara, Banten Bay. This research was conducted for three months from October to December 2019 with one month interval of sampling at six stations. Sample analysis and data analysis from January 2020 to September 2021. This study showed that the results of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) formed two groups of aquatic conditions characterized by the presence of Protozoa and rotifers. Water quality parameters affecting the life of plankton in Bojonegara waters consist of salinity (10-36 ppm), total phosphate (0.001-0.114 mg/L), nitrate and nitrite (0.553-0.713 mg/L and 0.011-0.245 mg/L). The abundance of zooplankton ranged from 3.02 to 175.55 ind/L. Nauplius is the most common type of zooplankton found. Based on the community structure formed during the rainy season, it can be seen that zooplankton can still grow well at the location and time of observation. This illustrates that the zooplankton community structure in Bojonegara waters is less stable.

INTRODUCTION

Banten Bay waters is one of the waters located in the northern area of the island of Java. These waters have various depths ranging from 2-20 meters (Rustam *et al.* 2018). These waters get a lot of pressure from their surroundings because there are industrial activities, sand mining, and community activities (Wisha *et al.* 2015). Bojonegara District is an area that is widely used. The very high intensity of industrial activities and the reclamation of coastal areas can trigger changes in the quality of the surrounding waters (Liyubayina 2018).

Water quality is water characteristics including substances, energy, and other components in waters that can be measured through physical, chemical, and biological parameters (Effendi 2003). Any changes in both parameters (physics and chemistry) can affect the life of aquatic biota, one of which is zooplankton. Zooplankton belongs to the type of plankton, namely microscopic animals that live floating or floating on the surface of the water (Nontji 2008).

Zooplankton that live on the water surface throughout their lives will form an interaction called community structure (Tyas *et al.* 2017). Zooplankton community structure is one of the main parameters to evaluate the

condition of a waters. The parts measured in the community structure include composition, abundance, diversity, dominance and evenness of zooplankton (Putra *et al.* 2012).

Zooplankton abundance means the number of zooplankton in individual units that can be found in one liter of sampled water. Zooplankton diversity means a parameter to get a picture of the primary productivity of a waters (Kowiati *et al.* 2019). The dominance of zooplankton means the state of the species that dominates a waters (Jannah and Muchlisin 2012). Zooplankton evenness means the distribution of zooplankton in the waters (Rikardo *et al.* 2016).

Changes in each parameter of the zooplankton community structure can indicate changing water conditions (Kheireddine *et al.* 2018). Therefore, research on the relationship between zooplankton community structure and water quality is very important to get an overview of the water conditions in Bojonegara District, Banten Bay.

METHODS

Time and Location

The research was conducted for three months from since October until December 2019. The time interval was one month sampling. Zooplankton and water's samples were carried out in the Bojonegara of Banten Bay (**FIGURE 1**) and at six stations (**TABLE 1**). Analysis of zooplankton was conducted at Micro Biology Laboratory I, Department of Aquatic Resources Management. Analysis of water quality parameters was conducted in situ and at Aquaculture Environment Laboratory, Department of Aquaculture, IPB University.

FIGURE 1. Location map of locations at Bojonegara waters, Banten Bay

The selection of station points for each location is based on activities in the vicinity and the direction of the water flow. The first station is closest to the mainland to the fourth station closest to the open sea. The last station is closest to the mouth of the river. The activities that are commonly found are Steampowered Electric Generator (PLTU) and sand mining. The following is the geographical position of each station in the waters of Bojonegara.

TABLE 1. Each research station position is geographically in Bojonegara waters

Station	Location Point		Location
	South Latitude (S)	East Longitude (E)	
Station 1	05°59.011'	106°05.426'	Settlement and shipdeck
Station 2	05°58.901'	106°06.558'	PT Samudra Marine Indonesia
Station 3	05°58.890'	106°07.713'	PLTU and plug chart
Station 4	05°59.682'	106°07.046'	PLTU
Station 5	05°59.773'	106°06.386'	Estuary
Station 6	06°00.053'	106°05.594'	River

Data Collection

Data collection was carried out primary and secondary. Primary data are the results of observations in the field (in situ) and the results of analysis in the laboratory. Secondary data is rainfall data obtained through online data of the Meteorological, Climatological, and Geophysical Agency (BMKG).

The water quality parameters observed in situ were transparency, color, pH, depth, temperature, dissolved oxygen, and water salinity. The water quality parameters observed in the laboratory were nitrate, nitrite, total phosphate, and Total Suspended Solid (TSS). At six stations, 50 liters of water were filtered for zooplankton sampling. This is done on the surface of the water that is 30 cm deep. Sampling of zooplankton with plankton net with a net mesh size of 30 “μ” m. The filtering results are stored in bottles made of polyethylene and then added Lugol's iodine preservative until it turns brown. The zooplankton samples were then analyzed in the laboratory (APHA 2017).

Water samples were carried out using a Van Dor water sampler. The water sample was then stored in a sample bottle made of polyethylene. The sample bottles were then stored in a coolbox filled with ice cubes for analysis in the laboratory (APHA 2017).

Abundance

The abundance of zooplankton including the biovolumes or densities of zooplankton in 1 liter of sample water (Garcia-Chicote *et al.* 2017). Calculation used a compound microscope binocular Zeiss Primo Star with a magnification of 10x10. Zooplankton identified referred to several identification books, including Yamaji (1979), Conway *et al.* (2003), Suthers and Rissik (2009). Zooplankton diversity was calculated using the Sedgewick-Rafter Cell (SRC) with the following formula.

$$\text{No./mL} = \frac{C \times 1000 \text{ mm}^3}{A \times D \times F}$$

Description:

- C = Number of organisms counted
- A = Area of a field, mm²
- D = Depth of a field (SRC depth), mm
- F = Number of fields counted

Evenness

Evenness index can describe the level of uniformity in the number of each species that is evenly distributed at each station and the absence of a tendency for species dominance in the zooplankton community (Odum 1996). The evenness index that is close to 1 means that the uniformity between species tends to be evenly distributed, whereas if it is close to 0 it means that the uniformity between species tends to be low (Dash and Dash 2009).

$$E = \frac{H'}{\log S}$$

Description:

- H' = Shannon Index
- S = Species amount

Dominance

The dominance index value close to 0 indicates that there is no dominant species, while if it is close to 1, it indicates that there is a certain type of dominance in the community. The dominant index used was Simpson's dominant index with the following formula (Krebs 1978).

$$D = \sum (ni/N)^2$$

Description:

ni = Individual type amount to-i
 N = Individual total amount

Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis is a multivariant analysis method that aims to present maximum information on the data matrix in the form of graphs. The matrix consists of zooplankton abundance variables as individuals (rows) and water quality parameter variables as quantitative variables (columns) to determine the relationship (Samudera *et al.* 2021). Analysis of the main components until now is widely used and considered important in quantitative ecological analysis (Ismunarti 2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Composition and Abundance of Zooplankton According to Sampling Time

The abundance of zooplankton in each month can be different. This is caused by changes in the aquatic environment which is influenced by various factors. There are three groups of zooplankton found. Based on **TABLE 2**, it can be seen the average abundance of zooplankton in the three months.

TABLE 2. Average abundance of zooplankton (Ind/L)

Organism	October	November	December
Protozoa			
<i>Eutintinnus</i> sp.		11.1	
<i>Favella</i> sp.	8.06	8.3	23.66
<i>Globorotalia</i> sp.	9.16	9.1	3.72
<i>Leprotintinnus</i> sp.	11.48	8.88	10.6
<i>Parafavella</i> sp.	4.21	3.81	17.81
<i>Tintinnopsis</i> sp.	35.33	11.46	32.47
Crustacea			
<i>Centropages</i> sp.		1.52	
Nauplius	31.17	175.55	163.65
<i>Oithona</i> sp.	1.58		
<i>Paracalanus</i> sp.	4.25		
Rotifera			
<i>Brachionus</i> sp.		29.41	3.02

The type of zooplankton that has the highest abundance is Nauplius. The abundance tends to be highest in each month. The type of zooplankton that has the lowest abundance is *Centropages* sp. The composition and abundance of zooplankton tends to be less than Nauplius.

Total Abundance of Zooplankton

It is important to know the total abundance of zooplankton based on time and sampling station. The following shows the total abundance of zooplankton in the three months and six stations (**FIGURE 2**).

FIGURE 2. Total abundance of zooplankton at Bojonegara waters, Banten Bay

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the abundance of zooplankton at each station fluctuated. This happened in the third month. The abundance of zooplankton at station 2 tends to be the highest among the other stations, which is 652,6 ind/L.

Composition and Abundance of Zooplankton Per Order Per Station

Each observation station has a different zooplankton composition. This difference in composition is influenced by the condition of the waters at the station. The following is the composition of each zooplankton at six stations (**FIGURE 3**).

(c)

FIGURE 3. The composition and total abundance of zooplankton in October (a), November (b), and December (c)

Based on the picture above, it can be seen that the group of protozoa has the highest composition in October and December. In November, the highest composition is crustaceans. The group of protozoa always appears every month of observation.

The Structure of Zooplankton Community

The structure of the zooplankton community is important to know. Divided into diversity index, evenness index, and dominance index. Below are the results of each index (**FIGURE 4**).

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 4. Value of diversity index (a), evenness index (b), and dominance index (c) zooplankton

Based on the three indexes above, it can be seen that the value of the evenness index tends to be inversely proportional to the value of the dominance index. The value of the diversity index tends to be directly proportional to the value of the evenness index.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis is very important to calculate to determine the relationship between zooplankton abundance and water quality parameters. Below shows the water quality parameters that have an influence on the abundance of zooplankton (**FIGURE 5**).

FIGURE 5. Biplot zooplankton three months of observation

Based on the results of the zooplankton biplot above, it can be seen that the Rotifera group has a close relationship with the parameters of salinity, total phosphate, nitrate and nitrite. The abundance of protozoa and crustaceans tends to be less affected by certain water quality parameters.

Discussion

The total abundance of zooplankton in the waters of Bojonegara, Banten Bay is around 24-490.62 ind/L. The abundance is quite fluctuating at each station. The highest abundance of total zooplankton was at Station 2 in November, while the lowest was at Station 2 in December. The high abundance at Station 2 in November can be influenced by the turbidity of the waters, which is 22 NTU. According to Siagian *et al.* (2019), the maximum value of turbidity levels in waters that are good for plankton growth is 25 NTU. Turbidity in Bojonegara waters is influenced by coastal mining or sediment dredging. This can cause the turbidity of the waters to increase. This can affect the life of plankton (Ernas *et al.* 2018).

Brightness of the waters at Station 2 in November is 108 cm. This is in accordance with the statement of Sin *et al.* (2013), namely low turbidity can result in increased brightness and light availability for plankton growth. Another factor that can affect the abundance of plankton in a waters is the season. October is included in the transition season. November and December are included in the rainy season. According to Nirmalasari *et al.* (2016), when the rainy season generally the nutrient levels in the waters will be lower than the dry season, so that the density of plankton will also be low.

According to Faturohman *et al.* (2016), PLTU produces waste that can cause sea surface temperatures to increase. This will greatly affect the quality of waters and aquatic biota, such as zooplankton. Indonesia's sea surface temperature range is 28-31°C. However, the waters around the disposal of industrial waste and steam power plants can experience an increase in temperature of up to 37°C (Ismayati *et al.* 2013). This is in accordance with the temperature obtained in the study ranging from 31.4-41°C.

Protozoa and crustacea groups are the groups that have the highest abundance of zooplankton in the waters compared to the Rotifera group. According to Velho *et al.* (2013), the protozoa group accounts for more than 50% of zooplankton production in the waters. Therefore, its abundance is found to be very high in the waters. According to Sari *et al.* (2014), crustaceans have a high adaptation to water because zooplankton can only survive and thrive if the aquatic environment is suitable. One of the most common types of crustaceans is nauplius (copepod).

This is in accordance with the statement of Ginting *et al.* (2015) that copepods are the dominant type of zooplankton found in marine waters. Therefore, the common copepod becomes the main food for small fish. The abundance of nauplius is most abundant at Station 2 in each month.

The water temperature at Station 2 ranges from 31.4-34°C. This is in accordance with the statement of Wati *et al.* (2019) that nauplius has a wide tolerance, that is, it can live in a temperature range of 6-35°C. Another thing that causes Nauplius to be found at each station is the light factor. The brightness of the waters at Station 2 ranges from 108-154.5 cm. This brightness is high because sunlight can penetrate the waters to a certain depth.

The value of the zooplankton diversity index ranged from 0.13 to 1.41. Based on the criteria of the Shannon-Weaner plankton diversity index (Odum and Barrett 2004), the diversity of zooplankton in the waters is low and the distribution of the number of individuals of each species is also low. According to Sudinno *et al.* (2017), low diversity indicates that Bojonegara waters are less suitable for zooplankton growth. This is because the pressure from the environment on the waters is quite high.

The zooplankton uniformity index value was relatively low, ranging from 0.03 to 0.42. This can illustrate that zooplankton have been able to adapt and compete in utilizing food. Prayan *et al.* (2014) stated that low plankton uniformity could indicate waters that have the potential for dominance of certain types of plankton. This can be caused by the instability of environmental factors and the population of microorganisms.

At Station 4 in October, the uniformity was very high and the dominance was very low. A high uniformity value can indicate that the uniformity between species is evenly distributed (Sari *et al.* 2014). According to Radiarta (2013), uniformity can describe the status of the trophic level in the waters. Spatially, the uniformity index generally has a similar pattern to the diversity index. However, this is not the case at this station.

The value of zooplankton uniformity tends to be inversely proportional to its dominance value. This happened at almost every station and month of observation, except for Stations 2, 4, and 5 in December. At Stations 3 and 4 in November, diversity and uniformity were very low, while dominance was very high. This shows that there are certain species that dominate the waters. Nauplius is the species that dominates both stations. Nauplius is a type of copepod. According to Lilis *et al.* (2019), copepods have a high ability to survive in different habitats and in the temperature range of 17-30°C.

At Stations 5 and 6 in October, the uniformity was quite high, while the dominance was very low. This shows that the aquatic environment is quite stable so that many types of zooplankton can survive. High uniformity indicates that the distribution of each individual species is quite even.

Water quality parameters have a relationship with the abundance of zooplankton at each observation station. The results of the PCA biplot illustrate the relationship between the physical and chemical parameters of the waters on the abundance of plankton (Pratiwi *et al.* 2018).

Activities around Station 1 are Fish Auction Place (TPI). This location can produce various kinds of waste that can affect the surrounding environment (Subhan 2018). For example, fish washing waste that is not properly treated is organic waste. The input of organic waste can increase the concentration of nutrients in the waters (Utami *et al.* 2016).

The results of the zooplankton biplot illustrate that the Protozoa group has a close relationship with temperature and Rotifera has a close relationship with the parameters of nitrate and nitrite, salinity, and total phosphate. Rotifers are generally used by phytoplankton as nutrients (Syafitri *et al.* 2021). Rotifers are only found at Station 6 in November and December. *Brachionus sp.* is the only species found.

Station 6 is located near the mouth of the river and estuary. This is appropriate because generally these locations are sources of runoff from disposal in the environment such as anthropogenic. *Brachionus sp.* is the type of zooplankton that is most widely used as the first exogenous food by marine fish larvae because its size is in accordance with the mouth opening of fish larvae (Ogello *et al.* 2018).

The water temperature throughout the month of observation ranged from 31.4-41°C. This is in accordance with the statement of Sikder and Xu (2020) that Protozoa have a wide life span related to water conditions, one of which is temperature, so that Protozoa can be found every month of observation. Water quality parameters such as temperature and salinity are parameters that generally affect zooplankton abundance. This is stated in the research of Syafitri *et al.* (2021) who took to observe the waters of Banten Bay.

Based on BMKG online data, the intensity of rainfall in October is 9.6 mm/hour. In November it is 11.1 mm/hour and in December it is 11.6 mm/hour. According to Nirmalasari *et al.* (2016), when the rainy season generally the nutrient levels in the waters will be lower than the dry season, so the density of plankton will also be low.

The zooplankton diversity index was categorized as medium, the uniformity index was categorized as high, and the dominance index did not indicate species dominance. Based on the community structure formed from the dry season to the transitional season, it shows that plankton can grow well at the location and time of observation. This illustrates that the waters of Bojonegara are in a stable condition.

The zooplankton diversity index is categorized as low, the uniformity index is categorized as low to moderate, and the dominance index indicates species dominance. Based on the community structure formed during the rainy season, it shows that plankton can still grow well at the location and time of observation. This illustrates that the waters of Bojonegara are in a less stable to stable condition.

The unstable condition of Bojonegara waters is caused by environmental pressure factors. Mining activities on the coast of Banten Bay are suspected of causing water pollution in the form of turbidity. Turbidity that exceeds the quality standard can affect the photosynthetic process of phytoplankton in the waters of Banten Bay (Ernas *et al.* 2018). Waste originating from residential areas, if not treated, generally provides input of organic and inorganic materials (Oktavia *et al.* 2019). The concentration of phosphate is thought to increase with the input of industrial waste (Hamuna *et al.* 2018). Any type of waste will not have a bad impact if it is managed properly. However, limited funds and a low level of awareness can indirectly cause waste to be not managed properly (Widiyanto *et al.* 2015).

CONCLUSION

The results showed of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) formed three groups of water conditions characterized by the presence of rotifers, protozoa, and crustacea. Based on the community structure formed during the rainy season, it can be seen that zooplankton can still grow well at the location and time of observation. Zooplankton community structures in Bojonegara waters reflect relatively unstable conditions, which are influenced by salinity and total phosphate conditions.

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